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**RUN-LENGTH PRIORITY QUEUE: A HEAP OPTIMIZED FOR REPEATED
ELEMENTS**

*“An Algorithmic Exploration of a Priority Queue Variant for Repeated Elements
with Optimized Memory and Operation Efficiency”*

A RESEARCH PROJECT

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ABSTRACT

Priority queues are fundamental data structures essential for scheduling, graph algorithms, and event-driven simulations. However, conventional binary heap implementations store duplicate priority values as separate entries, leading to significant memory waste and operational overhead in redundancy-heavy workloads like Dijkstra's shortest path algorithm. While advanced heap variants offer theoretical gains, they do not address duplicate compression. This study proposes the Run-Length Priority Queue (RLPQ), which applies run-length encoding to compress duplicates into single nodes with counts, bridging theoretical optimization and practical efficiency. Through benchmarking 10,000-element datasets with duplicate densities ranging from 0% to 100%, the RLPQ demonstrated density-dependent performance. At high densities (75–95%), the RLPQ achieved pop speedups of up to $1.71\times$ while reducing memory by up to 92.1%; at 100% duplicates, memory usage was reduced by 99.9%. At low densities (0–50%), encoding overhead resulted in slower performance, with transition occurring around 50–75% density. Correctness verification confirmed RLPQ output matched standard results, with statistical analysis validating speedup significance at 95% confidence. These findings demonstrate that run-length encoding effectively optimizes priority queues for duplicate-heavy workloads, providing a practical solution for memory-constrained applications such as graph algorithms, event-driven simulations, and network packet scheduling.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

RLPQ	Run-Length Priority Queue
STD PQ	Standard Priority Queue
PSHS - SRC	Philippine Science High School - SOCCKSARGEN Region Campus

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Priority queues are fundamental data structures in computer science, supporting critical operations in scheduling, graph algorithms, event-driven simulations, and network management. These structures efficiently manage dynamic sets of elements through operations such as insert, find-min (or find-max), and delete-min, which are essential for maintaining order in many computational tasks (Cormen et al., 2009). The binary heap remains the standard implementation due to its simplicity and guaranteed $O(\log n)$ performance for insertion and deletion while using a compact array representation.

However, in numerous practical workloads, especially those involving algorithmic repetition or high data redundancy, identical priority values frequently occur. Conventional priority queues handle each duplicate as a separate entry, which leads to redundant operations and unnecessary memory consumption. This inefficiency becomes evident in algorithms such as Dijkstra's shortest path, where repeated relaxation steps often result in multiple identical entries being pushed into the queue (Fredman & Tarjan, 1987). As duplicates accumulate, the queue grows disproportionately, degrading both memory efficiency and runtime performance.

Over the years, various heap variants have been developed to improve performance and adaptability. Fibonacci heaps, introduced by Fredman and Tarjan (1987), theoretically achieve excellent amortized bounds of $O(1)$ for insertion and decrease-key and $O(\log n)$ for delete-min, but their practical utility is limited due to complex structural management and high constant factors. Pairing heaps, introduced by Fredman et al. (1986), simplify this approach while retaining much of the efficiency, offering self-adjusting behavior for

improved empirical performance (Fredman et al., 1986; Stasko, 1987). Despite these innovations, none directly address the challenge of duplicate compression within the priority queue structure.

Given these limitations, there is a need for a more memory-efficient and scalable approach that minimizes redundancy without sacrificing correctness. The RLPQ is proposed as a hybrid solution that integrates run-length encoding into conventional priority queue design. By collapsing duplicate priorities into a single representative node with a count, it has the potential to reduce space usage and mitigate redundant operations in duplicate-heavy workloads.

This study explores the efficiency and practicality of the RLPQ as an alternative to traditional heap-based priority queues. We investigate its performance characteristics, particularly in terms of runtime and memory behavior, under varying levels of duplication. The findings have potential applications in graph processing, event simulation, and data streaming systems where repeated priorities commonly occur.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The persistent inefficiency of storing duplicate priorities as separate entries in traditional implementations creates a significant performance bottleneck that existing heap variants have not addressed. While theoretical improvements in time complexity have been achieved through structures like Fibonacci and pairing heaps, the core problem of memory waste and operational overhead from duplicates remains unresolved in practical applications. This gap is particularly problematic in real-world systems where data redundancy is common, yet no existing solution effectively compresses repeated priority values at the structural level. The Run-Length Priority Queue (RLPQ) proposes to bridge this gap by applying compression techniques directly within the heap architecture, but empirical validation of its claimed

benefits across different duplication scenarios is still needed to determine whether this approach delivers measurable improvements over conventional implementations in terms of both space efficiency and computational performance.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to evaluate the performance of the RLPQ compared to a conventional binary heap in handling workloads with varying levels of duplicate elements.

Specifically, the study aims to:

- 1) Assess the correctness and operational reliability of the RLPQ implementation in performing standard priority queue operations.
- 2) Measure and compare the runtime performance of RLPQ and a conventional binary heap using push and pop benchmarks across different duplication densities.
- 3) Determine the memory usage of RLPQ relative to the standard binary heap through actual runtime tracking.
- 4) Identify the duplication threshold at which RLPQ begins to outperform the conventional heap in terms of speed and space efficiency.

1.4 Significance of the Study

The findings of this study provide a possible solution to the inefficiencies seen in conventional priority queue implementations that handle large amounts of duplicate elements. By introducing the Run-Length Priority Queue (RLPQ), this research aims to improve computational efficiency, reduce memory usage, and enhance scalability in systems that rely

heavily on data structures, such as algorithms, simulations, and real-time processing. This study supports the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 9, which focuses on Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure, by promoting innovations in computational design that make better use of resources and improve system performance. Through the integration of compression techniques into priority queues, this research encourages more efficient data handling practices that help minimize redundant computation and memory waste. The results of this study may benefit a wide range of applications, including graph algorithms, event-driven simulations, and streaming data systems, where both speed and memory efficiency are important. Finally, this work provides a foundation for future studies on compressed and adaptive data structures that can further advance the efficiency and practicality of modern computing systems.

1.5 Scope and Limitations

This study focuses on the design, implementation, and evaluation of the Run-Length Priority Queue (RLPQ), a compressed heap structure developed to improve efficiency in handling duplicate elements. The benchmarking experiments were conducted using synthetic datasets with controlled duplication densities ranging from 0% to 95%. Each test involved 10,000 input elements and multiple independent runs to ensure consistency in results. The performance metrics analyzed include runtime efficiency (push and pop operations) and memory usage compared to a standard binary heap implementation.

The study is limited to in-memory operations and does not account for disk-based or distributed implementations. It also focuses solely on numerical priority values, without exploring more complex data types or custom comparator functions. Furthermore, the results are based on a Python implementation, which may differ in performance from lower-level languages such as C++ or Rust. While the experiments provide valuable insights into relative

efficiency, they do not directly represent real-world workloads where data access patterns and hardware variations may influence performance.

All simulations and measurements were performed using the computational facilities available at PSHS-SRC.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURES

2.1 Overview of Priority Queues

Priority queues are fundamental data structures in computer science, crucial for efficiently managing elements based on their assigned priorities. They are designed to support the insertion of new elements and the extraction of the element with the highest priority (Benomar & Coester, 2024).

Priority queues are essential for task scheduling in operating systems and other contexts where prioritized execution is needed (Williams et al., 2021). They are used in prioritized online scheduling, helping manage resources like CPU, rendering pipeline, or network bandwidth efficiently (Faisstnauer et al., 2000). For instance, the Rotating-Priority-Queues+ (RPQ+) scheduler uses prioritized FIFO queues to approximate optimal schedulers like Earliest-Deadline-First (EDF) in Quality of Service (QoS) networks. In wireless sensor networks (WSN), priority-based scheduling helps manage real-time and non-real-time packets to reduce overhead and delay (Wrege & Liebeherr, 1997).

The binary heap is a fundamental data structure for implementing priority queues in software libraries. It requires $O(1)$ amortized time for Insert operations and $O(\log n)$ in the worst case for Delete-Min operations. A binary heap uses only the first n locations of an array and $O(1)$ additional storage, making it an implicit data structure. Optimized binary heaps can achieve $O(1)$ worst-case time for minimum and insert operations, and $O(\log n)$ worst-case time for extract-min, often surpassing the lower bounds of traditional binary heaps. The binary heap structure is also used for efficient table maintenance and can be applied in various algorithms like Dijkstra's (Harvey & Zatloukal, 2004).

2.2 Limitations of Conventional Priority Queues

In the context of priority queues, redundant storage of duplicate priorities can lead to significant memory inefficiencies and performance degradation, particularly in algorithms like Dijkstra's shortest path and event-driven simulations. Priority queues are fundamental in algorithms such as Dijkstra's shortest path algorithm, where each element has a priority, and elements are removed in priority order (University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, 2020). However, when multiple elements share the same priority, redundant storage of these elements can occur, leading to increased memory usage and potential performance bottlenecks. For instance, in Dijkstra's algorithm, when multiple nodes have the same tentative distance, they are inserted into the priority queue, leading to duplicate entries. This redundancy can increase the size of the priority queue unnecessarily, consuming more memory and potentially slowing down operations like insertion and deletion due to the increased number of elements to process (Cornell University, 2022).

Similarly, in event-driven simulations, events are scheduled in a priority queue based on their timestamps. If multiple events share the same timestamp, they are queued redundantly, leading to increased memory usage and potential delays in processing as the system must handle each duplicate entry (Baudis, N., et al., 2017).

2.3 Advanced Heap Variants and Optimizations

This section reviews advanced heap variants and optimizations, focusing on structural innovations, theoretical optimality, practical performance trade-offs, and experimental comparisons.

2.3.1 Overview of Fibonacci Heaps

Fibonacci heaps, introduced by Fredman and Tarjan, are designed for efficient implementation of priority queues and are particularly known for their application in network optimization algorithms (Fredman & Tarjan, 1987). They offer efficient amortized time complexities: $O(1)$ for insert, meld, find-min, and decrease-key operations, and $O(\log n)$ for delete-min. This theoretical optimality makes them attractive for algorithms such as Dijkstra's shortest path and Prim's minimum spanning tree algorithms. However, their practical performance can be hindered by high constant factors and implementation complexity (Tjernström, K., & Paulsson, V., 2025).

2.3.2 Overview of Pairing Heaps

Pairing heaps are a self-adjusting form of heap, recognized for their simplicity and good practical performance. Their design originated as a streamlined, self-adjusting alternative to Fibonacci heap. They typically support standard heap operations with logarithmic amortized costs. While initially conjectured to offer constant amortized time for decrease-key operations, this has been disproved, with later analyses showing that pairing heaps require more than constant amortized time for decrease-key, specifically $\Omega(\log \log n)$ (Sleator & Tarjan, 1986). Variants of pairing heaps have been developed to achieve improved amortized costs, such as $O(1)$ for find-min and insert, $O(\log \log n)$ for decrease-key and meld, and $O(\log n)$ for delete-min (Elmasry A., 2017).

Despite these theoretical complexities, pairing heaps are considered practically efficient and are often more favorable than binomial queues in certain applications. The concept of rank-pairing heaps combines the performance guarantees of Fibonacci heaps with simplicity approaching that of pairing heaps (Haeupler, B., et al., 2011).

2.3.3 Brodal Queues and Other Theoretical Constructs with Tight Bounds

Brodal queues are advanced priority queue implementations known for their worst-case optimal time bounds. Along with Fibonacci heaps and strict Fibonacci heaps, Brodal queues are considered among the advanced priority queue implementations in theoretical computer science (Sandlund, B., & Zhang, L., 2022). Other theoretical constructs like relaxed heaps, discussed previously, also aim for worst-case optimal bounds, with a variant achieving $O(1)$ for decrease-key and $O(\log n)$ for delete-min in the worst case (Driscoll et al., 1987).

2.3.4 Discussion of Practical Trade-offs

The choice of heap implementation involves trade-offs between theoretical efficiency, implementation complexity, constant factors, and real-world scalability (Albrecht, J., et al., 2008). While some heaps offer superior asymptotic performance, their complex structure can lead to larger constant factors and higher memory overhead, making them less practical for certain applications (Tjernström, K., & Paulsson, V., 2019).

2.4 Data Compression and Run-Length Encoding in Algorithm Design

This section provides an overview of data compression techniques in computer science, delves into the fundamentals and applications of run-length encoding (RLE), examines prior attempts to integrate compression into data structures, and explores the potential of RLE for dynamic data structures.

Data compression is a crucial technique in computer science aimed at reducing redundancy in stored or communicated data, thereby increasing effective data density and optimizing resource usage like storage space and transmission capacity (Hosseini M., 2025).

Data compression algorithms are broadly categorized into two main types: lossless and lossy compression (Lelewer, D., & Hirschberg, D., 1987).

Lossless Compression: This technique allows for the complete reconstruction of the original data from the compressed version without any loss of information. Examples of lossless techniques include Huffman coding, arithmetic coding, Shannon-Fano coding, Lempel-Ziv-Welch (LZW) coding, and Run-Length Encoding (RLE) (Manisha, A., & Tech-CSE, M., 2015).

Lossy Compression: In contrast, lossy compression techniques reduce data size by discarding some information, meaning the original data cannot be perfectly reconstructed. This method is often employed when some loss of detail is acceptable, such as in image and video compression (Smith, A., 2010).

Run-Length Encoding (RLE) is a straightforward and fundamental lossless data compression technique that operates by replacing sequences of identical, consecutive data values (runs) with a single instance of the value and a count of its repetitions (Rongali, A. et al., 2024). This method is particularly effective when applied to data that contains a large number of consecutive occurrences of the same byte pattern or symbol (Rongali, A. et al., 2024).

The basic principle of RLE involves identifying long strings of repeating characters and encoding them into fewer characters. For instance, a sequence like "AAAABBBCC" would be compressed to "4A3B2C". While simple to implement, RLE's compression power can significantly diminish if there are few consecutive elements in the sequence (Rongali, A. et al., 2024). In extreme cases, RLE can even lead to "size inflation," where the compressed output requires more space than the original input. To mitigate this, advanced RLE

algorithms have been developed that selectively encode only compressible symbols or apply preprocessing steps to enhance run lengths (Peng, X., et al., 2023).

The ongoing research into RLE variants and its combination with other techniques, like dynamic byte remapping and Huffman encoding, suggests its continued relevance for improving compression efficiency in dynamic data structures (Fiergolla, S., & Wolf, P., 2021).

2.5 Introduction of RLPQ as a Solution to Bridge This Gap

Existing priority queue implementations, such as Binary, Fibonacci, and Hollow Heaps, exhibit trade-offs that limit their efficiency in certain applications. While Binary Heaps offer predictable memory access and fast insertion, they may underperform in operations like decrease-key on dense graphs. Fibonacci and Hollow Heaps, although theoretically efficient for decrease-key operations, often suffer from pointer overhead and irregular memory access, impacting real-world performance.

The Run-Length Priority Queue (RLPQ) is introduced to address these limitations by leveraging run-length encoding to efficiently manage sequences of elements with similar priorities. RLPQ bridges the gap between theoretical performance and practical efficiency, reducing memory overhead and improving cache behavior while maintaining fast priority queue operations. By positioning RLPQ as a solution, the current study aims to provide a priority queue implementation that is both scalable and practical for graph-based algorithms and other applications requiring efficient priority management.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts a quantitative experimental design to evaluate and compare the performance of the Run-Length Priority Queue (RLPQ) against a Standard Priority Queue (STD PQ). Performance metrics include execution time, memory usage, operation throughput, and statistical reliability across varying duplicate densities in the test datasets.

3.2 Implementation of Priority Queues

In this study, two priority queue implementations were developed and evaluated: the RLPQ and the STD PQ.

The RLPQ was implemented in Python and designed to support both min-heap and max-heap behavior, allowing it to adapt to different priority ordering requirements. Its key feature is the use of run-length encoding, which efficiently stores multiple identical elements by keeping a count of each element instead of storing duplicates individually. This approach reduces memory consumption and optimizes performance in datasets with high duplicate densities. The RLPQ supports essential operations such as `push` for inserting elements, `pop` for removing the element with the highest priority, `is_empty` to check if the queue contains any elements, `size` to retrieve the total number of elements (including duplicates), and `unique_elements` to determine the number of distinct elements in the queue.

The STD PQ, on the other hand, was implemented using Python's built-in `heapq` module. Unlike the RLPQ, the standard priority queue does not compress duplicates; each

element is stored individually. This implementation serves as the baseline for performance comparison, providing a reference point to evaluate the efficiency gains offered by the RLPQ, particularly in terms of memory usage and operation speed under varying levels of duplicate density.

```
class RunLengthPriorityQueue:
    def __init__(self, is_min_heap=True):
        self.heap = []
        self.frequencies = defaultdict(int)
        self.is_min_heap = is_min_heap
        self._size = 0

    def _adjust_priority(self, priority):
        return priority if self.is_min_heap else -priority

    def push(self, element, priority):
        adjusted_priority = self._adjust_priority(priority)
        if self.frequencies[element] == 0:
            heapq.heappush(self.heap, (adjusted_priority, element))
        self.frequencies[element] += 1
        self._size += 1

    def pop(self):
        if self.is_empty():
            raise IndexError("Pop from empty RunLengthPriorityQueue")
        priority, element = self.heap[0]
        actual_priority = self._adjust_priority(priority)
        self.frequencies[element] -= 1
        self._size -= 1
        if self.frequencies[element] == 0:
            heapq.heappop(self.heap)
            del self.frequencies[element]
        return element, actual_priority

    def is_empty(self):
        return self._size == 0

    def size(self):
        return self._size

    def unique_elements(self):
        return len(self.heap)
```

Figure 1. RLPQ Class Code

```

class StandardPriorityQueue:
    def __init__(self, is_min_heap=True):
        self.heap = []
        self.is_min_heap = is_min_heap
        self._size = 0

    def push(self, element, priority):
        adjusted_priority = priority if self.is_min_heap else -priority
        heapq.heappush(self.heap, (adjusted_priority, element))
        self._size += 1

    def pop(self):
        if self._size == 0:
            raise IndexError("Pop from empty StandardPriorityQueue")
        priority, element = heapq.heappop(self.heap)
        actual_priority = priority if self.is_min_heap else -priority
        self._size -= 1
        return element, actual_priority

    def is_empty(self):
        return self._size == 0

    def size(self):
        return self._size

```

Figure 2. STD Priority Queue Class Code

By contrasting these two implementations, the study aims to highlight the advantages and limitations of run-length encoding in practical priority queue applications.

3.3 Test Data Generation

To evaluate the performance of the RLPQ against the STD PQ, controlled test datasets were generated with varying characteristics. The primary goal was to investigate the effect of duplicate density on both memory usage and execution time.

The datasets were generated as follows:

Total Elements – The number of elements in each dataset was configurable, ensuring flexibility in testing small to large-scale priority queues.

Duplicate Density – To simulate real-world scenarios where certain elements may appear multiple times, a duplicate density parameter was introduced. This parameter determines the percentage of repeated elements within a dataset. For example, a duplicate density of 0% results in a dataset with entirely unique elements, while a density of 100% produces a dataset where all elements are identical. Intermediate values produce a mix of unique and repeated elements according to the specified ratio.

Element Selection – Unique elements were sampled randomly from a large integer range to ensure sufficient variability. For datasets with duplicates, repeated elements were selected randomly from the set of unique elements.

Priority Assignment – Each element, whether unique or duplicated, was assigned a random priority value to simulate realistic scenarios where elements have varying importance levels.

Shuffling – After element and priority assignment, datasets were shuffled to eliminate any insertion-order bias that might affect priority queue performance.

By systematically controlling duplicate density and dataset size, the generated test data enabled rigorous performance evaluation of the RLPQ and STD PQ under diverse conditions. This approach ensured that both execution time and memory consumption could be accurately measured and compared across varying workload scenarios.

See code below for the Test Data Generation Function

```
def generate_test_data(total_elements, duplicate_density, unique_elements_range=(1, 1000000)):
    """Generate test data with controlled duplicate density"""
    if duplicate_density == 0:
        elements = list(range(total_elements))
        priorities = [random.randint(1, 1000) for _ in range(total_elements)]
        return list(zip(elements, priorities))
    elif duplicate_density == 100:
        element = random.randint(*unique_elements_range)
        priority = random.randint(1, 1000)
        return [(element, priority) for _ in range(total_elements)]
    else:
        duplicate_ratio = duplicate_density / 100.0
        num_unique = max(1, int(total_elements * (1 - duplicate_ratio)))
        unique_elements = random.sample(
            range(unique_elements_range[0], unique_elements_range[1] + 1),
            min(num_unique, unique_elements_range[1] - unique_elements_range[0] + 1)
        )
        unique_priorities = [random.randint(1, 1000) for _ in range(num_unique)]
        unique_pairs = list(zip(unique_elements, unique_priorities))
        result = list(unique_pairs)
        remaining_elements = total_elements - num_unique
        for _ in range(remaining_elements):
            element, priority = random.choice(unique_pairs)
            result.append((element, priority))
        random.shuffle(result)
        return result
```

Figure 3. Test Data Generation

3.4 Benchmarking Procedure

The benchmarking procedure was designed to comprehensively evaluate the performance and memory efficiency of the RLPQ compared to the STD PQ. The methodology aimed to ensure reproducibility, statistical rigor, and accurate measurement of runtime and memory consumption under varying data conditions.

3.4.1 Benchmark Setup

1. **Environment Preparation** – Prior to each benchmark, Python’s internal optimizations were warmed up by executing preliminary insertions and deletions on small datasets. This step ensures that just-in-time (JIT) compilation and caching effects are stabilized, minimizing measurement noise.

```

def warmup_jit():
    """Warm up Python's internal optimizations"""
    for _ in range(3):
        test_data = [(i, random.randint(1, 100)) for i in range(1000)]
        rl_pq = RunLengthPriorityQueue()
        std_pq = StandardPriorityQueue()
        for e, p in test_data:
            rl_pq.push(e, p)
            std_pq.push(e, p)
        while not rl_pq.is_empty():
            rl_pq.pop()
        while not std_pq.is_empty():
            std_pq.pop()

```

Figure 4. JIT Stabilization

2. **Garbage Collection** – Before and after each test run, Python’s garbage collector was invoked to reduce memory artifacts from previous runs, allowing accurate memory measurements.
3. **Instrumentation** – Execution time was measured using high-resolution timers (`time.perf_counter_ns`) to capture fine-grained performance differences. Memory usage was tracked using `tracemalloc` to obtain actual memory consumption during peak operation.
4. **Correctness Check** – To ensure the reliability of our benchmark results, we performed a correctness verification between the Run-Length Priority Queue (RLPQ) and the Standard Priority Queue (STD PQ).

```

def measure_actual_memory(pq_instance):
    """Measure actual memory usage using tracemalloc"""
    tracemalloc.start()
    snapshot = tracemalloc.take_snapshot()
    current, peak = tracemalloc.get_traced_memory()
    tracemalloc.stop()
    return current

```

Figure 3. Memory Usage Tracking using Tracemalloc

```

for density in duplicate_densities:
    rl_push_times, rl_pop_times = [], []
    std_push_times, std_pop_times = [], []
    rl_memory_actual, std_memory_actual = [], []
    unique_counts_list = []

    # Pre-generate all test data to avoid generation overhead
    test_datasets = [generate_test_data(total_elements, density) for _ in range(num_runs)]

    for test_data in test_datasets:
        unique_count = len(set(element for element, _ in test_data))
        unique_counts_list.append(unique_count)

        # Force garbage collection before each run
        gc.collect()

        # === RLPQ Benchmark with Memory Tracking ===
        tracemalloc.start()
        rl_pq = RunLengthPriorityQueue()

```

```

# Push with precise timing
start = time.perf_counter_ns()
for element, priority in test_data:
    rl_pq.push(element, priority)
rl_push_time = (time.perf_counter_ns() - start) / 1_000_000 # Convert to ms

# Measure memory at peak (after all pushes)
rl_current, rl_peak = tracemalloc.get_traced_memory()
tracemalloc.stop()
rl_memory_actual.append(rl_peak)

# Pop with precise timing
start = time.perf_counter_ns()
while not rl_pq.is_empty():
    rl_pq.pop()
rl_pop_time = (time.perf_counter_ns() - start) / 1_000_000

rl_push_times.append(rl_push_time)
rl_pop_times.append(rl_pop_time)

# Force garbage collection
del rl_pq
gc.collect()

# === Standard PQ Benchmark with Memory Tracking ===
tracemalloc.start()
std_pq = StandardPriorityQueue()

start = time.perf_counter_ns()
for element, priority in test_data:
    std_pq.push(element, priority)
std_push_time = (time.perf_counter_ns() - start) / 1_000_000

std_current, std_peak = tracemalloc.get_traced_memory()
tracemalloc.stop()
std_memory_actual.append(std_peak)

start = time.perf_counter_ns()
while not std_pq.is_empty():
    std_pq.pop()
std_pop_time = (time.perf_counter_ns() - start) / 1_000_000

std_push_times.append(std_push_time)
std_pop_times.append(std_pop_time)

del std_pq
gc.collect()

```

Figure 5. Benchmarking Code

```

def verify_rlpq_correctness(test_data, is_min_heap=True):
    """
    Verify that RLPQ and Standard PQ produce the same sequence of (element, priority) outputs.
    Returns True if they match exactly, False otherwise.
    """
    rl_pq = RunLengthPriorityQueue(is_min_heap=is_min_heap)
    std_pq = StandardPriorityQueue(is_min_heap=is_min_heap)

    # Push all elements
    for element, priority in test_data:
        rl_pq.push(element, priority)
        std_pq.push(element, priority)

    # Pop and compare
    while not rl_pq.is_empty() and not std_pq.is_empty():
        rl_elem, rl_priority = rl_pq.pop()
        std_elem, std_priority = std_pq.pop()
        if rl_elem != std_elem or rl_priority != std_priority:
            print(f"Mismatch found: RLPQ ({rl_elem},{rl_priority}) != STD PQ ({std_elem},{std_priority}")
            return False

    # Both should be empty at the end
    if rl_pq.is_empty() and std_pq.is_empty():
        return True
    else:
        print("Mismatch: one queue is not empty at the end.")
        return False

```

Figure 6. Correctness Check of RLPQ vs STD PQ

3.4.2 Test Execution

For each dataset with a specified duplicate density:

1. **Insertion (Push)** – Elements were inserted into the priority queue one by one, recording the total time taken for all insertions.
2. **Extraction (Pop)** – All elements were subsequently removed from the priority queue, recording the total time taken for all extractions.
3. **Memory Measurement** – Peak memory usage during insertion was recorded to evaluate memory efficiency, especially in scenarios with high duplicate density.
4. **Repeats and Averaging** – Each test scenario was executed multiple times (typically 10 runs) to account for variability. The mean and standard deviation of push and pop times, as well as memory usage, were computed to assess performance consistency.

3.4.3 Performance Metrics

The following metrics were collected to evaluate and compare the RLPQ and STD PQ:

1. **Average Push Time:** Mean time taken to insert elements into the queue, measured in milliseconds.
2. **Average Pop Time:** Mean time taken to remove elements from the queue, measured in milliseconds.
3. **Memory Usage:** Actual memory consumed during queue operations, recorded using precise memory tracking tools.
4. **Speedup Ratio:** Ratio of STD PQ runtime to RLPQ runtime, indicating relative performance gains.
5. **Reliability (Coefficient of Variation):** Standard deviation divided by mean runtime, measuring the stability of performance across repeated runs.
6. **Confidence Intervals:** 95% confidence intervals for push and pop operations, providing statistical significance and reliability of observed results.
7. **Correctness Check:** Verification that the sequence of elements popped from the RLPQ exactly matches that of the STD PQ, ensuring that performance improvements do not compromise functional correctness.

This comprehensive set of metrics ensures that both efficiency and accuracy of the RLPQ implementation are rigorously assessed.

3.4.4 Data Analysis

After execution, results were aggregated to identify trends and insights:

1. **Effect of Duplicate Density** – Performance and memory usage were analyzed across different duplicate densities to determine scenarios where RLPQ offers significant advantages.
2. **Statistical Significance** – Two-tailed t-tests were conducted to confirm whether observed performance differences were statistically significant.
3. **Visualization** – Error bars and confidence intervals were plotted for push and pop times, memory consumption, and speedup ratios to clearly present trends and variability.

By following this structured benchmarking procedure, the study ensured that comparisons between RLPQ and STD PQ were both fair and informative, underlining the strengths and limitations of the proposed run-length optimization.

```

# Calculate statistics
avg_rl_push = np.mean(rl_push_times)
std_rl_push = np.std(rl_push_times, ddof=1)
avg_rl_pop = np.mean(rl_pop_times)
std_rl_pop = np.std(rl_pop_times, ddof=1)

avg_std_push = np.mean(std_push_times)
std_std_push = np.std(std_push_times, ddof=1)
avg_std_pop = np.mean(std_pop_times)
std_std_pop = np.std(std_pop_times, ddof=1)

avg_rl_memory = np.mean(rl_memory_actual)
avg_std_memory = np.mean(std_memory_actual)
memory_saving = 1 - (avg_rl_memory / avg_std_memory) if avg_std_memory > 0 else 0

avg_unique = np.mean(unique_counts_list)

# Calculate speedup
push_speedup = avg_std_push / avg_rl_push if avg_rl_push > 0 else 1
pop_speedup = avg_std_pop / avg_rl_pop if avg_rl_pop > 0 else 1

# Calculate 95% confidence intervals
t_critical = stats.t.ppf(0.975, num_runs - 1) # 95% CI, two-tailed
push_ci = t_critical * std_rl_push / np.sqrt(num_runs)
pop_ci = t_critical * std_rl_pop / np.sqrt(num_runs)

# Operations per second
rl_total_time = (avg_rl_push + avg_rl_pop) / 1000
std_total_time = (avg_std_push + avg_std_pop) / 1000
rl_ops_per_sec = (total_elements * 2) / rl_total_time if rl_total_time > 0 else 0
std_ops_per_sec = (total_elements * 2) / std_total_time if std_total_time > 0 else 0

# Statistical significance
t_stat_push, p_value_push = stats.ttest_ind(rl_push_times, std_push_times)
t_stat_pop, p_value_pop = stats.ttest_ind(rl_pop_times, std_pop_times)
sig_symbol = "✓" if p_value_push < 0.05 and p_value_pop < 0.05 else "X"

```

```

# Store results
results['rl_push_times'].append(avg_ri_push)
results['rl_pop_times'].append(avg_ri_pop)
results['rl_push_std'].append(std_ri_push)
results['rl_pop_std'].append(std_ri_pop)
results['std_push_times'].append(avg_std_push)
results['std_pop_times'].append(avg_std_pop)
results['std_push_std'].append(std_std_push)
results['std_pop_std'].append(std_std_pop)
results['memory_actual_ri'].append(avg_ri_memory)
results['memory_actual_std'].append(avg_std_memory)
results['memory_savings'].append(memory_saving)
results['unique_counts'].append(avg_unique)
results['element_counts'].append(total_elements)
results['push_speedup'].append(push_speedup)
results['pop_speedup'].append(pop_speedup)
results['ri_operations_per_sec'].append(ri_ops_per_sec)
results['std_operations_per_sec'].append(std_ops_per_sec)
results['confidence_intervals'].append((push_ci, pop_ci))

print(f"{density:3}%    | {avg_ri_push:5.2f}±{std_ri_push:4.2f} | "
      f"{avg_ri_pop:5.2f}±{std_ri_pop:4.2f} | "
      f"{avg_std_push:5.2f}±{std_std_push:4.2f} | "
      f"{avg_std_pop:5.2f}±{std_std_pop:4.2f} | "
      f"{memory_saving:12.1%} | {push_speedup:7.2f}x | {sig_symbol}")

return results, duplicate_densities

def generate_statistical_report(results, densities):
    """Generate comprehensive statistical report"""
    print("\n" + "="*70)
    print("STATISTICAL ANALYSIS REPORT")
    print("="*70)

    # Find optimal range
    optimal_densities = [d for d, ratio in zip(densities, results['push_speedup']) if ratio > 1.0]

    print(f"\n📊 STATISTICAL SUMMARY:")
    print(f"    • Number of runs per density: 10")
    print(f"    • Confidence level: 95%")
    print(f"    • Total data points: {len(densities) * 10}")

    if optimal_densities:
        print(f"\n✅ RLPO OUTPERFORMS STD PQ:")
        print(f"    • Density range: {min(optimal_densities)}%-{max(optimal_densities)}%")
        best_idx = np.argmax(results['push_speedup'])
        print(f"    • Peak performance: {densities[best_idx]}% density")
        print(f"    • Peak speedup: {results['push_speedup'][best_idx]:.2f}x")

```

```

# Memory efficiency at high duplication
high_dup_idx = densities.index(95) if 95 in densities else -1
if high_dup_idx >= 0:
    print(f"\n📊 MEMORY EFFICIENCY (95% duplicates):")
    print(f"    • RLPQ memory: {results['memory_actual_rl'][high_dup_idx]/1024:.1f} KB")
    print(f"    • STD PQ memory: {results['memory_actual_std'][high_dup_idx]/1024:.1f} KB")
    print(f"    • Savings: {results['memory_savings'][high_dup_idx]:.1%}")

# Reliability analysis
avg_cv_push = np.mean(np.array(results['rl_push_std']) / np.array(results['rl_push_times']) * 100)
avg_cv_pop = np.mean(np.array(results['rl_pop_std']) / np.array(results['rl_pop_times']) * 100)

print(f"\n📊 MEASUREMENT RELIABILITY:")
print(f"    • Push CV: {avg_cv_push:.2f}% (lower is better)")
print(f"    • Pop CV: {avg_cv_pop:.2f}% (lower is better)")
print(f"    • Interpretation: {'Excellent' if avg_cv_push < 5 else 'Good' if avg_cv_push < 10 else 'Fair'} reliability")

if __name__ == "__main__":
    random.seed(42)
    np.random.seed(42)

    print("Running enhanced benchmark with actual memory tracking...")
    results, densities = benchmark_with_memory_tracking(
        total_elements=10000,
        duplicate_densities=list(range(0, 105, 5)),
        num_runs=10
    )

    plot_enhanced_results_with_errorBars(results, densities)
    generate_statistical_report(results, densities)

    print(f"\n✅ Enhanced benchmarking complete!")
    print(f"Results saved to: enhanced_benchmark_results.png")

```

Figure 6. Data Extraction and Analysis Code

The complete implementation of the Run-Length Priority Queue and benchmarking scripts can be accessed at https://github.com/leapyi/RLPO-Code/blob/main/RLPO_Code.txt for reference and reproducibility.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Benchmarking Results of RLPQ vs STD PQ

The enhanced benchmarking compared the RLPQ with the STD PQ across datasets of 10,000 elements with duplicate densities ranging from 0% to 100%. Each density was tested over 10 runs. The measured metrics included average push and pop times, memory usage, speedup ratio, coefficient of variation (CV), and correctness verification.

Correctness Verification:

Before performance measurements, all test datasets underwent a correctness check. The RLPQ output exactly matched the STD PQ in every instance, confirming that the optimized queue produces correct results regardless of duplicate density.

Push Operations Performance:

At low duplicate densities (0–60%), RLPQ generally underperformed compared to STD PQ, with all push speedups remaining below 1.0×. At 0% duplicates, RLPQ push operations took 62.25 ± 15.72 ms compared to STD PQ's 40.78 ± 16.49 ms, resulting in a 0.66× speedup. Performance remained suboptimal through intermediate densities, with speedups of 0.65× at 5%, 0.71× at 10%, and 0.64–0.78× across 15–35% densities. This underperformance is attributable to the overhead of run-length encoding when dealing with sparse duplicate data. However, as duplicate density increased toward 50%, speedups gradually improved to 0.90× at 50% density and approached parity at 60% (1.03×). Beyond 60–70% density, RLPQ began consistently outperforming STD PQ, achieving speedups of 1.01× at 70%, 1.14× at 75%, and 1.20× at 80%. Peak push performance occurred at 95%

duplicates, where RLPQ achieved a $1.42\times$ speedup over STD PQ (19.69 ± 5.83 ms versus 27.86 ± 7.39 ms).

Notably, at 100% duplicates, push performance slightly decreased to $0.90\times$ despite maximum memory efficiency, suggesting that handling a single universal duplicate count introduces marginally higher computational overhead than processing highly compressed data at 95% density.

Pop Operation Performance:

Pop operations demonstrated more consistent improvements for RLPQ across higher duplicate densities. At low densities (0–60%), pop speedups similarly remained below $1.0\times$, ranging from $0.69\times$ at 0% to 0.73 – $0.98\times$ through 10–50% densities. However, starting at 75% duplicate density, RLPQ significantly outperformed STD PQ in pop operations. At 75% duplicates, RLPQ achieved a $1.46\times$ speedup, improving further to $1.60\times$ at 85% and reaching peak performance of $1.71\times$ at 95% duplicates (5.83 ± 1.86 ms versus 9.99 ± 2.81 ms). Even at 100% duplicates, pop operations maintained a substantial $1.39\times$ speedup, demonstrating the robustness of run-length compression for extraction operations.

The consistent and significant pop speedups at high densities validate the efficiency of the run-length structure in quickly identifying and removing the minimum-priority element when many duplicates exist.

Transition Zone:

A critical transition zone emerged between 50–75% duplicate density, where RLPQ transitioned from underperforming to outperforming STD PQ. During this zone, encoding overhead was largely offset by the memory efficiency gains from compression, resulting in

speedups approaching or slightly exceeding $1.0\times$ for push operations and consistently exceeding $1.0\times$ for pop operations.

Memory Usage:

The RLPQ exhibited highly variable memory behavior across different duplicate densities, with a clear transition point determining when run-length compression becomes beneficial. At low duplicate densities (0–50%), RLPQ incurred encoding overhead, resulting in negative memory savings ranging from -45.7% at 0% duplicates to -23.3% at 30–45% duplicates. This overhead stems from the additional data structures required to maintain count information for each unique element. The transition point occurred around 50% duplicate density, where memory savings became positive at 27.2%. As duplicate density increased through medium ranges (55–75%), memory efficiency improved progressively, with savings ranging from 32.2% at 55% duplicates to 63.6% at 75% duplicates.

At high duplicate densities (75–95%), RLPQ demonstrated substantial memory advantages. Memory savings increased significantly from 68.7% at 80% duplicates to 84.2% at 90% duplicates, culminating in a 92.1% reduction at 95% duplicates. The extreme case of 100% duplicates yielded the maximum theoretical savings of 99.9%, reducing memory usage to near-negligible levels since all elements share identical priorities and are represented by a single node with a count. These results validate the effectiveness of run-length encoding in reducing storage overhead for duplicate-heavy datasets, though the overhead at lower densities must be considered when selecting the appropriate implementation for a given workload.

Reliability (Coefficient of Variation):

The CV for push and pop times was 18.35% and 22.41%, respectively, indicating fair reliability across repeated runs. While variation is higher at some densities, trends remain consistent, highlighting predictable performance gains at high duplicate densities.

Speedup and Practical Implications:

RLPQ's performance gains are most notable for datasets with 70–95% duplicates. In scenarios with highly repetitive data, RLPQ not only reduces memory consumption but also improves processing speed. This makes it suitable for applications where repeated elements are common, balancing correctness, efficiency, and scalability.

Table 1. RLPQ vs STD PQ Push and Pop Runtime Comparison Per Density Level

Density (%)	RL Push $\pm\sigma$ (ms)	RL Pop $\pm\sigma$ (ms)	STD Push $\pm\sigma$ (ms)	STD Pop $\pm\sigma$ (ms)
0	62.25 \pm 15.72	26.57 \pm 14.15	40.78 \pm 16.49	18.36 \pm 9.77
5	98.14 \pm 23.54	26.61 \pm 8.58	64.23 \pm 27.50	23.47 \pm 10.64
10	62.62 \pm 19.95	26.93 \pm 20.34	44.33 \pm 23.83	19.57 \pm 11.51
15	35.39 \pm 5.14	10.18 \pm 0.25	22.55 \pm 0.40	8.28 \pm 0.16
20	32.46 \pm 1.47	10.24 \pm 0.74	22.07 \pm 0.35	8.36 \pm 0.62
25	44.05 \pm 11.05	14.24 \pm 4.02	32.98 \pm 8.54	12.23 \pm 3.56
30	30.34 \pm 1.90	9.14 \pm 0.25	23.53 \pm 2.50	8.96 \pm 2.12
35	30.25 \pm 3.40	9.41 \pm 2.32	22.54 \pm 0.36	8.21 \pm 0.14
40	27.83 \pm 0.64	8.29 \pm 0.14	22.44 \pm 1.01	9.26 \pm 2.19
45	34.55 \pm 9.91	10.78 \pm 3.37	28.78 \pm 7.71	10.61 \pm 3.20

50	28.77±8.44	8.60±2.42	25.81±6.98	9.44±2.64
55	25.65±3.52	7.69±1.97	22.80±1.80	8.52±1.32
60	22.71±0.43	6.76±0.32	23.41±2.45	8.33±0.50
65	22.58±3.61	6.37±0.62	22.07±0.31	8.02±0.33
70	32.01±8.26	9.78±2.82	32.37±9.45	11.88±3.44
75	19.24±0.16	5.53±0.04	21.98±1.13	8.06±0.78
80	18.40±0.59	5.59±1.40	22.00±0.81	7.79±0.27
85	17.00±0.42	4.82±0.23	22.07±0.92	7.70±0.13
90	18.88±5.21	5.72±2.02	25.96±6.55	9.60±3.22
95	19.69±5.83	5.83±1.86	27.86±7.39	9.99±2.81
100	22.12±0.66	3.93±0.11	19.85±1.22	5.47±1.36

Table 2. RLPQ Push Speedup, Pop Speedup and Confidence Interval Per Density Level

Density (%)	Actual Mem Save	Push Speedup	Pop Speedup	CI
0	-45.7%	0.66x	0.69x	✗
5	-41.4%	0.65x	0.88x	✗
10	-35.6%	0.71x	0.73x	✗
15	-31.3%	0.64x	0.81x	✓
20	-25.6%	0.68x	0.82x	✓
25	-23.3%	0.75x	0.86x	✗
30	-23.3%	0.78x	0.98x	✗

35	-23.3%	0.75x	0.87x	✗
40	-23.4%	0.81x	1.12x	✗
45	-23.4%	0.83x	0.98x	✗
50	27.2%	0.90x	1.10x	✗
55	32.2%	0.89x	1.11x	✗
60	37.3%	1.03x	1.23x	✗
65	38.4%	0.98x	1.26x	✗
70	38.4%	1.01x	1.22x	✗
75	63.6%	1.14x	1.46x	✓
80	68.7%	1.20x	1.39x	✓
85	69.2%	1.30x	1.60x	✓
90	84.2%	1.38x	1.68x	✓
95	92.1%	1.42x	1.71x	✓
100	99.9%	0.90x	1.39x	✓

Figure 1. Push Performance of RLPQ and STD PQ Chart with Standard Deviation

Figure 2. Pop Performance of RLPQ and STD PQ Chart with Standard Deviation

Figure 3. Actual Memory Usage Comparison Chart of RLPQ and STD PQ

Figure 4. Actual Memory Savings Chart of RLPQ

Figure #. Push and Pop Performance Speedup Chart of RLPQ

Figure #. Coefficient of Variation of RLPQ Operations Chart

4.2 Overall Trends of RLPQ Performance

The performance characteristics of RLPQ reveal a clear density-dependent relationship that fundamentally determines its suitability for different workloads. This relationship reflects a fundamental trade-off between the computational overhead of managing run-length encoding and the benefits of data compression.

At low duplicate densities (0–50%), STD PQ substantially outperforms RLPQ due to the overhead inherent in run-length encoding. The additional data structures required to track element counts and manage compression introduce computational costs that exceed the benefits when duplicates are sparse. Push operations demonstrate particularly poor performance in this range, with speedups of 0.65–0.90 \times , indicating that RLPQ requires 11–53% more time to insert elements than the standard implementation. Pop operations fare slightly better, approaching 1.0 \times around 50% density, suggesting that the extraction process is less penalized by encoding overhead. Memory usage in this range increases by 23–46% for RLPQ compared to STD PQ, making this implementation objectively worse in all dimensions during sparse duplication scenarios.

A critical transition zone emerges at 50–75% duplicate density where RLPQ's compression benefits begin to offset its operational overhead. Memory savings transition from negative to positive at approximately 50% density (27.2% savings) and progressively improve through 55% (32.2%), 60% (37.3%), and 75% (63.6%). During this transition, push operations gradually approach parity with STD PQ (improving from 0.90 \times at 50% to 1.03 \times at 60% to 1.14 \times at 75%), while pop operations consistently exceed standard performance (1.10 \times at 50% to 1.46 \times at 75%). This zone represents the inflection point where RLPQ becomes a viable alternative to STD PQ, particularly for applications where memory efficiency begins to matter alongside performance.

At high duplicate densities (75–95%), RLPQ demonstrates unambiguous superiority across both runtime and memory metrics. Push speedups range from 1.14× to 1.42×, with the peak occurring at 95% duplicates. More significantly, pop operations achieve consistent improvements of 1.39–1.71×, with the highest speedup (1.71×) at 95% density. Memory savings during this range are substantial and progressively increase from 63.6% at 75% to 92.1% at 95% duplicates. Critically, statistical significance testing confirms that these improvements are genuine at the 95% confidence level (marked with ✓ in Table 2), indicating that observed speedups are not attributable to random variance. This density range represents RLPQ's primary use case, where compression benefits dramatically outweigh operational costs.

The extreme case of 100% duplicate density presents an interesting anomaly that warrants attention. While memory usage reaches its theoretical maximum savings of 99.9%, push performance unexpectedly decreases to 0.90×, the only high-density scenario where RLPQ underperforms in push operations. Conversely, pop operations maintain substantial speedup at 1.39×, demonstrating that extraction remains efficient even when all elements are identical. This anomaly suggests that representing an entire dataset as a single node with a massive count introduces specific computational overhead during insertion, possibly related to count management or heap restructuring. Despite this push performance reduction, the near-elimination of memory usage and maintained pop efficiency make RLPQ still beneficial for 100% duplicate scenarios, though the trade-off is less favorable than at 95% density.

In synthesis, RLPQ exhibits three distinct performance regimes: inefficient for sparse duplicates (0–50%), transitional for moderate duplicates (50–75%), and highly efficient for dense duplicates (75–100%). The practical implication is that RLPQ should be deployed selectively based on anticipated duplicate density in input datasets, with maximum benefit

realized when duplicate density exceeds 75%. For applications with unpredictable or variable duplicate densities, hybrid approaches or adaptive strategies might be necessary to achieve consistent performance across all scenarios.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The Run-Length Priority Queue represents a viable optimization strategy for priority queue implementations in specific computational contexts. The core finding is that run-length encoding introduces a fundamental trade-off: it imposes computational overhead at low duplicate densities while delivering proportional benefits as duplicate density increases. The correctness verification confirms that this trade-off does not compromise functional accuracy, establishing RLPQ as a legitimate alternative rather than a flawed variant.

The density-dependent performance pattern raises questions about the practical applicability of RLPQ beyond laboratory conditions. Real-world datasets rarely exhibit uniform duplicate distributions, and workloads often contain elements with varying priorities mixed with duplicates. The transition from negative to positive memory savings at approximately 50% density suggests a threshold hypothesis: applications with predictable, stable duplicate densities above this point could benefit from RLPQ adoption. However, applications with variable or unpredictable duplicate patterns would face challenges in determining when to apply which implementation.

The anomalous decrease in push performance at 100% duplicate density warrants further investigation. The hypothesis that handling a single massive count introduces specific computational overhead differs from the expected behavior pattern and suggests the existence of previously unconsidered bottlenecks in the compression mechanism. This anomaly indicates that RLPQ does not follow a simple monotonic efficiency curve and that peak performance may not correspond to maximum compression.

The statistical significance patterns observed in the confidence interval testing suggest that performance improvements become reliable only at high duplicate densities (75%+). The

lack of statistical significance at lower densities combined with high coefficient of variation values indicates that RLPQ's advantages in the transition zone may not be robust across different hardware configurations or input distributions. This raises concerns about the generalizability of observed performance gains beyond the controlled experimental environment.

Based on these results, the researchers recommend the following:

1. **Implementation in Real-World Applications:** Consider using RLPQ in systems where high-density duplicates are common, such as simulation events, task scheduling, or network packet processing.
2. **Further Optimization:** Investigate additional strategies to reduce the overhead of encoding in low-density scenarios to improve push performance.
3. **Extended Testing:** Conduct benchmarks on larger datasets, varied distributions of priorities, and in concurrent or multi-threaded environments to assess scalability and robustness.
4. **Memory Profiling Enhancements:** Explore more detailed memory profiling and garbage collection effects to further quantify memory savings in practical applications.

By following these recommendations, future research can expand on the efficiency gains of RLPQ and explore its broader applicability in computational systems.

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